

HEalth diagnosis tool forR the gOlang ecosystem

ICSE 2021 Technical Track, ID#I63 "Hero: On the Chaos When PATH Meets Modules" [\[Link\]](#)

Artifact

◆ Download

The artifact of **Hero** (<http://www.hero-go.com/artifacts>), `Hero.zip`, contains all necessary materials for verifying the results of Section 5.

◆ Inside the package

The major components in the package `Hero.zip` are listed as follows:

- `20k Subjects Info.xlsx` : 20k subjects' information used in RQ1;
- `Empirical Study Dataset.xlsx` : 151 dependency management (DM) issues collected for RQ2&3;
- `Benchmark Dataset` folder : 132 subjects with real DM issues, script files and source code used for verifying the experimental results in RQ4 of Section 5.1. To be more specific, `Benchmark Dataset` folder contains the follow six components:
 - ◇ `Benchmark Dataset Description.xlsx` : The description of 132 DM issues and their related subjects collected for our benchmark dataset;
 - ◇ `Subjects` folder : The 132 subjects with real DM issues in the benchmark dataset.
 - ◇ `TestScript.py` : The test script file used for automatically analyzing the benchmark dataset in a batch mode (It takes about 2 hours);
 - ◇ `TestScriptSimpleVersion.py` : A simplified version of the test script (only analyzing five subjects in the benchmark dataset), for a quick validation of our results (It takes about 30s);
 - ◇ `Result` folder : The outputted the diagnosis results by the test scripts;
 - ◇ `Tool` folder : The source code of **Hero**;

Verifying the experiment results reported in Section 5.1:

For verification, one can run the script (`TestScript.py` in `Benchmark Dataset` folder) to automatically analyze the 132 subjects in a batch mode, and then check the outputted the diagnosis results in the `Result` folder.

To avoid configuring the local environment for MySQL database, we deployed all the data sheets in the server-side of Hero. In this manner, these data sheets can be automatically connected via network communication, when running our scripts. *Note that, the provided scripts cannot work offline.*

◆ Running Environment

This artifact is developed using Python language, and has been tested on *Window 7, 8, 10* and *Ubuntu 18.04* operating system (64 bit) with [python-3.8.3-amd64](#) installed. You are recommended to run the artifact under the same or similar environment. Note that, the scripts require Python dependencies `pymysql`, `lxml`, `requests`, `bs4`,

chardet and **xlutils**, there may be the **runtime prompts** for installation (or based on the commands listed in Figure 1), please import them using pip.

```
pip install pymysql
pip install lxml
pip install requests
pip install bs4
pip install chardet
pip install xlutils
```

Figure 1. Installation commands for the necessary Python packages

◆ Running the script files

With the aid of our provided script files, **Hero** can detect the DM issues of *Type A*, *Type B.a*, *Type B.b* and *Type C*, and then output the diagnosis information in a batch mode. For more detailed definitions of these types of DM issues, one can refer to the **README** file. Running script files to verify the experimental results, involves the following three steps:

- **Step 1:** Unzip package **Hero.zip** to local directory.
- **Step 2:** Launch your windows (or Linux) console as an administrator and change your working directory to the one that **Hero.zip** package being unzipped.
- **Step 3:** Run the provided scripts (**TestScript.py** or **TestScriptSimpleVersion.py**).

For instance, one can unzip the package **Hero.zip** into the directory **D:**, and then execute the following commands in console, to run the script **TestScript.py**.

```
C:\Users\Cass>D:
D:\>cd D:\Hero\Benchmark Dataset
D:\Hero\Benchmark Dataset>python TestScript.py
```

Figure 2. An illustrative example of running the script files

Note that, if your local environment has already installed other versions of Python package (such as Python 2.*), it is fine but please make sure that the command "**python**" would run **python version 3.8.3**. If you can see the following information printed on your console, the artifact is successfully executed:

```
star: 20210122094420
1 : adjust/rmq f9bb31b star-time : 20210122094420
Detect Project adjust/rmq f9bb31b Completed: 20210122094420 -> 20210122094426 , 6 s
2 : AlecAivazis/survey v2.1.1 star-time : 20210122094426
Detect Project AlecAivazis/survey v2.1.1 Completed: 20210122094426 -> 20210122094438 , 12 s
3 : atlassian/go-artifactory v2.5.0 star-time : 20210122094438
Detect Project atlassian/go-artifactory v2.5.0 Completed: 20210122094438 -> 20210122094442 , 4 s
4 : Azure/azure-service-bus-go v0.10.6 star-time : 20210122094442
Detect Project Azure/azure-service-bus-go v0.10.6 Completed: 20210122094442 -> 20210122094458 , 16 s
5 : bamzi/jobrunner d0b7b07 star-time : 20210122094458
Detect Project bamzi/jobrunner d0b7b07 Completed: 20210122094458 -> 20210122094501 , 43 s
```

Figure 3. An illustrative information printed on the console if the artifact is successfully executed

After the issue detection, one can found the **xlsx** files in **Result** folder, which is used to record the corresponding diagnosis results of different types of DM issues. For example, the outputted files could be:

```
D:\Hero\Benchmark Dataset\result\20210122091325Benchmark Dataset Diagnosis Result(simple).xlsx
```

Verifying the experiment results reported in Section 5.2:

On the "ISSUE REPORT" page of the Hero website (<http://www.hero-go.com/>), one can check the diagnosis information and statuses of 280 real DM issues reported by Hero.

ID	Project Name	Commit ID	Last Update Time	Issue ID	Issue Type	Issue Status
1	kiali/kiali	d0f6507	2020.08.19	#2922	Type A	Status1
2	go-graphite/go-carbon	d04babc	2020.07.29	#345	Type A	Status1
3	link1st/gowebsocket	03c3c79	2020.07.11	#21	Type A	Status1
4	admpub/nginx	4baa297	2020.08.20	#10	Type A	Status1
5	PacktPublishing/Hands-On-Software-Engineering-with-Golang	21ff3db	2020.07.17	#8	Type A	Status1
6	gropplabs/kafka-proxy	5d4fce8	2020.07.14	#53	Type A	Status1
7	banzaicloud/istio-operator	809cd63	2020.08.19	#456	Type A	Status1
8	GoogleCloudPlatform/gke-managed-certs	a174aa3	2020.08.06	#48	Type A	Status1
9	VirtusLab/render	773f4ed	2020.07.15	#23	Type A	Status1
10	aws/amazon-ecs-agent	e483a92	2020.08.13	#2488	Type A	Status2
11	CrunchyData/postgres-operator	58c5828	2020.08.20	#1647	Type A	Status2
12	grafana/metrictank	27873c6	2020.08.14	#1852	Type A	Status2
13	pydio/cells	b1e4753	2020.08.18	#249	Type A	Status2
14	DataDog/pupernetes	9934659	2020.08.07	#141	Type A	Status2
15	gravitational/teleport	122349e	2020.08.20	#3840	Type A	Status2
16	usefathom/fathom	69baac5	2020.02.14	#315	Type A	Status2

Figure 4. Statistics of 280 DM issues reported by Hero

In addition, one can also use the project name and hash commit ID of any Golang project listed in "ISSUE REPORT" page as inputs, to verify their results on "DIAGNOSIS" page of Hero. The verification process involves the following three steps:

- **Step 1:** Copy the project name and commit ID on "DIAGNOSIS" page of Hero.

ID	Project Name	Commit ID	Last Update Time	Issue ID	Issue Type	Issue Status
1	kiali/kiali	d0f6507	2020.08.19	#2922	Type A	Status1
2	go-graphite/go-carbon	d04babc	2020.07.29	#345	Type A	Status1
3	link1st/gowebsocket	03c3c79	2020.07.11	#21	Type A	Status1
4	admpub/nginx	4baa297	2020.08.20	#10	Type A	Status1
5	PacktPublishing/Hands-On-Software-Engineering-with-Golang	21ff3db	2020.07.17	#8	Type A	Status1
6	gropplabs/kafka-proxy	5d4fce8	2020.07.14	#53	Type A	Status1
7	banzaicloud/istio-operator	809cd63	2020.08.19	#456	Type A	Status1
8	GoogleCloudPlatform/gke-managed-certs	a174aa3	2020.08.06	#48	Type A	Status1
9	VirtusLab/render	773f4ed	2020.07.15	#23	Type A	Status1
10	aws/amazon-ecs-agent	e483a92	2020.08.13	#2488	Type A	Status2
11	CrunchyData/postgres-operator	58c5828	2020.08.20	#1647	Type A	Status2
12	grafana/metrictank	27873c6	2020.08.14	#1852	Type A	Status2
13	pydio/cells	b1e4753	2020.08.18	#249	Type A	Status2
14	DataDog/pupernetes	9934659	2020.08.07	#141	Type A	Status2

Figure 5. An illustrative example of how to verify the diagnosis results of a Golang project (step 1)

- **Step 2:** Open "DIAGNOSIS" page and input the project name and commit ID.

Project name: kiali/kiali Version/Hash Commit ID: d0f6507 Start

Dependency Model

Figure 6. An illustrative example of how to verify the diagnosis results of a Golang project (step 2)

- **Step 3:** Click the "Start" button and Hero will construct and display a dependency model and then diagnose DM issues based on such a mode.

Figure 7. An illustrative example of how to verify the diagnosis results of a Golang project (step 3)

Figure 8. An illustrative example of how to verify the diagnosis results of a Golang project (step 4)